

Preventive Measures Against White Collar Crime in India

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Received : 05/05/2024 1st BPR : 11/05/2024 Revised: 18/05/2024 2nd BPR : 30/05/2024 Accepted : 10/06/2024

Abstract

This research analyses is based on the concepts of white collar crime in India which serves as the foundation for this study's analysis. The term "white collar crime" refers to crimes that are committed by educated, upper-class individuals in the course of their employment. It is also known as the crime committed by elites who are "educated" and "professional." The common types of white-collar crimes that have emerged in India over the past few years and how they have evolved into socio-economic crimes have been the subject of additional discussion. Generally, a person is not a born criminal. A person becomes a criminal when some *social, economic, political, educational or psychological circumstances* force him to do so. In criminology, a criminal is punished for a crime on the basis of his mental intent. Unless he has the mental intent to commit a crime, no penal law punishes him. Saint Augustine was the first to discuss this. That in order to punish any person for any crime, it is necessary for him to have the mental intent to commit that crime.

Key words: White Collar Crime, India, Prevention.

Introduction

This research analyses is based on the concepts of white collar crime in India which serves as the foundation for this study's analysis. The term "white collar crime" refers to crimes that are committed by educated, upper-class individuals in the course of their employment. It is also known as the crime committed by elites who are "educated" and "professional." The common types of white-collar crimes that have emerged in India over the past few years and how they have evolved into socio-economic crimes have been the subject of additional discussion.

White-collar crimes are typically committed by individuals with advanced knowledge of fields such as finance management, engineering, medicine, organizational theory, and information technology, among others, and typically take place within large, complex organizations. The damage brought about by White Collar Crimes is, generally speaking, substantial. For instance, tax evasion resulted in less money going to the Treasury, bribery resulted in skewed government decisions, and inside trading resulted in investors losing their investments. There is moral intricacy and vulnerability in middle class violations which isn't apparent in different offenses. White-collar crime has a significant financial impact on businesses. To compensate for the misfortune, these organizations increment the cost of their item, which decreases the quantity of customers who get it. This is based on the law of demand, which says that demand falls when the price of a product goes up, and rises when the price goes down, all other things being equal. The company's loss has led to a reduction in employee compensation. The business frequently fires several workers. It becomes hard for the organizations to reimburse their advances. As a result, getting credit is becoming increasingly difficult for individuals.

White collar crimes are those committed by high-status individuals and are distinct from traditional crimes in that they involve a fundamental breach of trust through unethical business practices motivated by financial gain. The criminal law has always been regarded as the most fascinating area of

law. Everyone, lawyers and non-lawyers alike, enjoys discussing it. However, our perception of white-collar crime is somewhat biased. While it certainly fascinates us on one hand: Why do well-paid professionals commit it alone, with coworkers, or as part of a group effort across the entire organization? Who endures when an organization shifts numbers around on a calculation sheet? Who is to be accused when it has large number of representatives and layers of administration? The opportunity to commit a crime is the root cause of white-collar crime. Hirsch and Gottfredson (1987) described white-collar crime as different from other common crimes because they violate the law and are not the same as common crime. In addition, there are different responses from authorities between white-collar crime and common crime (Hirsch and Gottfredson, 1987). Cubicle crime was defined by Edwin Sutherland as "crime committed by a person of respectable and high economic standing in the course of his occupation." Since the term was coined by Sutherland during his speech to the American Sociological Society in 1939, there has been debate about what specific violations would be considered judicial violations. In general and in vague terms, peaceful crimes for monetary gain fell under this category. The most well-known activities under judicial crimes include antitrust violations, various types of misrepresentation, insider trading, and violations of natural law. The powers of members of government are also curtailed through other means of regulating the law, and public corruption and illegal tax evasion are included under salaried crimes.

Definition & Meaning of White Collar Crime

Late of Edwin Sutherland defined a White Collar Crimes as: "A person of upper Socio-economic class who violates the criminal law in course of occupational or professional activities"¹. The above definition of white collar crime has 5 characteristics.

- a. It is a crime,
- b. It is committed by a respectable person;
- c. One who has a high social status in the society?
- d. One who commits it in the course of his profession or business?
- e. It is generally a breach of trust or good faith.

Thus, **Prof. E. Sutherland** pointed out that "besides the 'traditional crimes or Blue collar crimes. Such as Assault, robbery, dacoit, Murder, Rape, Kidnapping and other acts involving violence, White Collar Crimes may be divided into Occupational Crime and Organizational Crime." According to the FBI, "a key agency that investigates these offenses, these crimes are characterized by deceit, concealment, or violation of trust." The motivation for these crimes is "to obtain or avoid losing money, property, or services or to secure a personal or business advantage."² WCC are the violations perpetrated by an individual of high societal position and decency throughout his occupation. A wrongdoing is carried out by salaried expert specialists or people in business and that normally includes a type of monetary robbery or misrepresentation. These are non-violent crimes committed by business people who are able to obtain large amounts of financial gain through a variety of deceptive tactics. White collar crime involves a wide range of activities and is committed by individuals who are otherwise involved in legitimate businesses. Until their crime is discovered, the perpetrators hold respectable positions in the communities. White-collar criminals can still expect much shorter sentences than other types of criminals in some countries. As a result, it was not included in the category of "Traditional or Conventional Crimes" even though it has the potential to cause significant harm to businesses. Some of the commendable steps that can help reduce such crimes that threaten to cripple our economy include the recent initiatives taken by our policymakers, ranging from amendments to be made in the Companies Act 2013, an entirely new approach to insolvency to be implemented through the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, proposed amendments to the Indian Penal Code and the introduction of the Fugitive Economic Offenders Act, 2018..

Nature of White Collar Crime

The next step is to determine the nature of these crimes after examining the definitions and distinctive characteristics of white collar crime. "a legal wrong that can be followed by criminal proceedings that

may result in punishment" is an offense or crime. The violation of the law is the defining characteristic of criminality. Regarding the nature of white collar crime, there are two opposing perspectives. One viewpoint asserts that white collar crimes are in fact "crimes," while the opposing viewpoint questions their criminality. White-collar crimes should not be included in the category of "crimes," according to those who argue that the vast majority of white-collar legislation is administrative in nature, focuses primarily on the business and professional classes of our society, and is based on a regulatory rather than penal philosophy. The majority of white-collar violations statutes are administrative in nature. The authority in question has complete discretion over whether or not a penal action should be taken. Because it is against the law, it is studied in the field of criminology, which makes sense. White collar crimes are still crimes, but they differ from traditional crimes in five ways: origin, responsibility determination, philosophy, enforcement, and penalties and trial procedures. The main argument is that some people believe these regulatory crimes are "civil," while others believe they are "criminal." The majority of white collar crime statutes impose civil and criminal penalties for the same offense. As a result, there are a plethora of options for prosecuting white-collar crimes, which is the source of this confusion. The main distinction that exists is the legitimate strategy in common cases varies from those of criminal cases. Numerous offenses like carelessness, criticism, trespass and so forth. can be tried under tort law as well as the Indian Penal Code (IPC), 1860. The Civil Procedure Code of 1908 governs cases involving torts, whereas the Criminal Procedure Code of 1973 governs cases involving criminal law. The argument that white collar crime is not really a crime because offenders are dealt with under civil law loses much of its strength if some forms of illegal behavior are dealt with by tort law rather than criminal law due to tradition or administrative reasons.

Reason of White Collar Crime

Generally, a person is not a born criminal. A person becomes a criminal when some *social, economic, political, educational or psychological circumstances* force him to do so. In criminology, a criminal is punished for a crime on the basis of his mental intent. Unless he has the mental intent to commit a crime, no penal law punishes him.

Saint Augustine was the first to discuss this. That in order to punish any person for any crime, it is necessary for him to have the mental intent to commit that crime. According to Freud, a person's mental state makes him a criminal because it has been observed that despite two people being in the same circumstances, one person becomes a criminal and the other person works hard to get out of that situation.

For example, a poor person brings up his family by driving a rickshaw, but another person chooses the path of theft or suicide to get out of the same situation. Mr. Freud has clarified this through his studies. In this way, it can be said that a person is not born a criminal but he is made a criminal by the social, economic, political or educational conditions of his society. Such people generally become big criminals whom we call white collar criminals. In this way, it can be said that a person's psychology also affects a lot in making him a criminal.

Difference Between White Collar Crimes and Economic Crimes

"White Collar Crime" applies to peaceful, monetarily inspired wrongdoing executed by business and government authorities while monetary offenses are violations that have a monetary part. These offenses are committed while participating in some type of financial or business activity. In spite of the fact that the term "economic offences" While some parts of the world, such as the United States, have defined crimes, India still lacks precise definitions. This can make it challenging to identify types of crimes.

Historical Background of White Collar Crime

The first white collar crime was recorded in America in 1473 which is called the Carrier Case. In this case, the agent was entrusted with the task of transporting some quantity of wool from one place to another. The person or the agent who was trusted was found guilty of stealing the wool for his own

use. After this case, the English court adopted the doctrine of 'breaking the bulk' which means that the bailee who was given the possession of the goods tried to break it and misuse the contents.

A. HISTORY OF WHITE COLLAR CRIME IN INDIA

i. **Ancient Times** - It is an undisputed fact in history that ever since humans started living together, the incidence of crime has increased. Some types of crimes have become obsolete and many new types of crimes have taken a different dimension in the present society. White collar crime is not a new phenomenon.

In the ancient and medieval literatures of India numerous³ in the references are found about these crimes since Vedic period. **Mannu**, "the great law giver of India felt that there was an age when 'dharma' prevailed in perfection but gradually 'adharmā' made its headway giving rise to the tendencies like theft, falsehood and fraud." Corruption may be a type of white collar crime, but it has always been the most discussed topic in all fields - social, economic and political, however, no strict steps/actions have been taken to stop this widespread evil. But if strict steps are not taken to stop it, then it will be dangerous not only for the country but for the whole world.

A. According to Brihaspati, in earlier times people were very virtuous and devoid of evil tendencies. Now greed and hatred have taken root in them. Bribery is not a new thing in India. Bribery is also mentioned in many Holy Scriptures.

B. **Narada** says "what has been given by men with fear, anger, lust, grief or in jest or by mistake or through any fraudulent practice by a minor, an idiot, a person not his own master, one insane or intoxicated, an outcast or in consideration of work unperformed be considered as given or bribe".

C. **Hindu Dharmashastra** writers always think for the better society, therefore Smrtikars take into consideration the problem of health and disease of the people. In this context they discard non-eatables whose sale is punishable. *Yajnavalkya* first pointed out that "sale of the dog's meat is an offence and those connected with such sale must be penalized. Their hands, nose and ears are to be mutilated besides pecuniary fines". *Vijnaneswara* commenting on "this verse also mentions that nose, ears, hands, the three organs of the body should be mutilated".

Kautilya "has propose damputation of hand and leg for the sale of non-eatable meat punishment of physician. The embryology was thoroughly known in ancient India and removal of immature foetus was taken as crime and the highest sin."

KathakaSamitha decries and mentions along with *Maitrayini Samitha* the removal of foetus is more severe crime than killing of a Brahmin. *Yajnavalkya* - "has keenly looked to this heinous crime and has proposed serious penalty to the person responsible for the destruction of embryo." According to *Kautilya* manufacture of forged coins is called '*Kutarupa Kara*' and one who mints coins in any place other than the government mint or without being supervised by the state mint maker is a counterfeit coin maker. *Kautilya* gives a list of apparatus that the counterfeit coin-maker used. They are metals alkali, charcoal, bellows, clipper, hammer, anvil, designed die and crucible."

B. Modern Period

The last quarter of 18th century saw the establishment of some cotton textile and jute mills in India but this did not much change the complexion of things because the British government had adopted a policy of some toleration towards the labour in India which was in fact primarily directed by reason and motives of preservation of the textile industry of Manchester and Lancashire in view of the competition between the two. Before the conditions of the India factory workers could much deteriorate the Factories Act, 1881 was placed on the statue book. In India rapid industrialization started only with the First World War (1914 to 1919) but even then the policy of the British Government was to artificially restrict the same to the minimum needed. Nevertheless even this limited industrial development was of an important social consequence since it saw the birth and growth of two new social classes in the Indian society -

(1) The industrial capitalist and

(2) The modern working class

Types of White Collar Crimes in India

India is a developing country and the trend of white collar crimes in India poses a threat to the economic development of the country. These crimes require immediate intervention by the government by not only making strict laws but also ensuring its proper implementation.

The ambit of white collar crimes is varied. Some of the white collar crimes that have been reported in India are:

Bank Fraud- Bank fraud is a criminal act where a person, withdraws money by illegal means either money or assets from the bank. Sometimes fraud also occurs when a person falsely represents him to be a bank or financial institution and withdraws money or assets from the people. Therefore we can say that bank fraud can be done in two ways:

1. By using illegal means to withdraw money or assets from the bank or any financial institution.
2. By wrongly representing oneself to be a bank or any financial institution, the person takes money or assets from people. Bank frauds are punishable in India under the IPC, 1860. Various sections like Section 403 which deals with criminal misappropriation of property, section 405 which deals with criminal breach of trust, section 415 which deals with cheating, section 463 deals with forgery and section 489A deals with counterfeiting of currency, deals with the crime of fraud in banks.

Types of Bank Fraud-

Counterfeit Monetary, Foundations, Cheating through checks Counterfeit, Credit endorsements, Bookkeeping Extortion and Wire Transfer Fraud- A fictitious website under the name "Rail Vikas Nigam Limited" was allegedly created by three individuals from West Bengal and Orissa. The website presented false information regarding job opportunities to individuals. Narayan Patra and Govind Sinha were the accused people who were taken into custody. The casualties griped that any data with respect to working of the organization, its accomplishments, and different ads were being accounted for on the authority site yet no enlistments were occurring. According to livemint.com, the number of bank fraud cases has increased at an unprecedented rate. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) released a report in 2017-18 stating that 5,916 cases of bank fraud totaling 41,167.03 crores were reported. This covered high-profile fraud cases like Vijay Mallya's and Nirav Modi's. Credit Card Frauds-These frauds are committed when one person uses the credit card of another person unauthorized to obtain goods of value, he is said to have committed credit card fraud against the other person. For example, in 2003 in Mumbai, Amit Tiwari, a 21 years old engineering student was arrested for using too many names, for having too many bank accounts and too many clients, all false managed to defraud a Mumbai-based credit card company, CC Avenue, of around 9 lakhs rupees. This case brought to the notice of the authorities that credit card frauds have not been recognized by the Information Technology Act, 2000. The loophole in the law has caused a great loss to the company. As per the report released by the Economic Times, it was found that over 900 cases of credit/debit cards and internet banking have been registered during the period of April-September, 2018. All these cases involved an amount of 1 lakh rupees and above. Minister of State for Electronics and IT (2018), S.S. Ahluwalia, informed that the Reserve Bank of India by 30th September, 2018 had registered a total of 921 cases of credit/debit card fraud. In 2017 a Metropolitan Magistrate became a victim of credit/debit card where the victim received two messages for two transactions done from his debit card, not in India, but abroad. The victim claimed that those transactions did not have his consent. A complaint of cheating under Section 420 of the Indian Penal Code, 21860 was filed. Fraud with the Insurance Company, Fraud in buying and purchasing of securities, Currency Schemes, Fraud in welfare activities.

Blackmail

Segment 503 of the Indian Reformatory Code, 1860 characterizes extorting or criminal terrorizing as, making an interest for cash or some other thought by burden of danger to cause actual injury, or to make harm ones property, or to blame one for a wrongdoing, or to uncover someone' secret. The following methods can be used to create the threat:

1. By revealing a person's secret, which the perpetrators are aware would greatly embarrass the victim. Take, for instance, the circumstance in which A, the managing director of the business XYZ, is aware that B, a female employee of the same business, was having a child with someone other than her husband. A requested that B commit fabrication on the record papers so he could steal 20 lakhs rupees from the organization without anyone being familiar with it, or probably he would uncover her mysterious which would cause incredible shame not exclusively to her however her family too.

Extortion - Extortion is a crime under section 383 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860. When one party coerces another party for payment of money, or property or services, he is said to have committed the crime of extortion. It is called a white collar crime because an officer may use his official right and make use of his higher position in the company to threaten another person for giving money, or transferring property, or for providing services.

The important elements which constitute the crime of extortion as laid down in the case of *People v. Fort*, are:

- There should be a communication of demands by one party to another
- In order for the fulfilment of the demands, the other party or his family should be threatened to cause some injury
- There should be intent to extort money from the other party for some advantage. The other party should be threatened to do or not to do something.

For example, David Letterman, an American television host, was extorted for a sum of \$2 million in case of involvement in sexual relationships with female employees. The suspect, Robert Halderman, was later caught and punished. In another case, a famous actress and model, Cindy Crawford and her husband became a victim of dollar 100,00 extortion case where their daughter's picture in which she was tied and gagged was to be revealed in the public if the couple did not adhere to the demands of the suspect⁴.

Fake employment placement rackets - There have been many cases where a student or a person looking for a job has been deceived by offenders who claim to provide placement or jobs to them and later on run away with the money they have taken as an advance to provide them with employment. **Section 66D** of the Information Technology Act, 2000 states the penalties to be imposed on a person for cheating on another person through personation using computer resources. For example, Ajay Kolla, the CEO of Wisdom Jobs was arrested along with 13 other staffs in January, 2019 on the charge of false recruitment. Wisdom Jobs was an award-winning recruitment firm which was established in the year 2009. Since then, Ajay Kolla had duped around 1.04 people, earning nearly 70 crore rupees out of fake placement promises as reported by the **Economic Times**.

Bribery- Bribery is the crime of asking for money, a favor, or something of value in exchange for the performance of another person's work. As a white-collar crime, bribery is typically committed in exchange for favor from a higher-up. The parties involved committed a crime. The majority of our country's public officials frequently encounter it. The discipline for pay off has been given under Segment 171E of the Indian Reformatory Code, 1860 which says that any individual who commits such an offense would be detained for a term which might stretch out to 1 year or with fine or both. Additionally, public officials who engage in activities that fall under this heading have been subject to sanctions under Section 13 of the Prevention of Corruption Act of 1988. The Prevention of Corruption (Amendment) Act of 1988 defines bribery as "any public official demanding or exchanging something in return for performing his duty which he is bound to perform within the power of his office."

Cybercrime

Cybercrime is on the rise because more people are using computers and the internet. Cybercrime refers to crimes that involve the use of a computer as well as the internet. The computer is used to commit cybercrime as a weapon or object. As in a genuine an individual illicitly have somebody's financial balance or Visa subtleties, in cybercrime the programmer encroaches into the individual subtleties connected with the record or charge card to get to the assets, to make buys or to run phishing tricks. In some cases the utilization of utilizing pernicious programming one can get close enough to the secret individual data, individual even illicitly conveys that information which the law restricts from distributing, such as, dispersing porn. Trafficking and stalking of any individual are also examples of

this kind. The Information Technology Act, 2000 arrangements with regulation of Cybercrime. Because it is impossible to define a crime of this nature involving computers and the internet, no statutes or laws have provided a specific definition of cybercrime.

Cybercrime subcategories in the Indian scenario:The major types of cybercrimes prevalent in India are as follows: Cybercrimes for Government Information A crime against the government is called cyber terrorism. This includes crimes like hacking government websites, military websites or distributing propaganda. These criminals are usually terrorists or enemies from different nations. Recently use of software named Pegasus spyware⁵ which was developed designed by country Israel Company NSO Group was widely in news regarding infecting data of many Government officials as well as people.

Major Cases Relating To Cyber Terrorism

The website of the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC) at Trombay was hacked in 1998. The hacker's gained access to the BARC's computer system and pulled out virtual data. In 2002, numerous prominent Indian web sites notably that of the Cyber Crime Investigation Cell of Mumbai was defaced. Messages relating to the Kashmir issue were left on the home pages of these web sites. In the *Purulia arms drop case*, the main players used the internet extensively for international communication, planning and logistics. In 2007, the two Indian doctors involved in the *Glasgow airport attack* used computers for terrorists' activities⁶. 2 men were identified by Police as *Bilal Abdullah (Muslim Doctor at The Alexandra Hospital)*⁷ & Kafeel Ahmad. Former Indian President, Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam- has expressed "concern over the free availability of sensitive spatial pictures of nations on the internet. He pointed out that the internet could be utilized effectively for gathering information about the groupings of terrorists. According to him, earth observation by "Google Earth" was a security risk to the nation".

Preventive Measures White Collar Crimes

While shopping in the market, it is suggested that customers bring bills with them, so that dishonest traders can be prevented from evading taxes. The Right to Data Act, 2005 is a strong weapon in the fight against corruption, it is the responsibility of the government to make more and more people aware of it and it is also the responsibility of law universities and colleges to make people aware of the law. The political race platform of every ideological group should include designs to solve the issue of white collar crime as well as the legitimate execution of white collar crime rules. A public complaint center should be set up by the government so that citizens can file complaints against white collar criminals. This threat can also be reduced if negative information about white collar criminals is made public. But its far-reaching effect will be that it will become easier to trace white collar criminals. And white collar criminals should not get tickets from political parties. Apart from this, their pledge to tackle white collar crime should be included in the manifesto of political parties. The Act defines and prohibits active concealment of facts, fraud, dishonest concealment, deceptive intent and lays down the principle of FRAUS OMNIA VITIATE, which means that anyone who enters into a contract through fraudulent conduct will be deemed to have violated the Act.

The Act criminalizes corruption and related unhealthy practices. The Act defines public duty, public servant and public authority and also clarifies its ambition to curb white-collar crimes as suggested by the Sanatan Committee Report (1964). The Act curbs corporate white-collar crimes such as non-compliance of provisions, mismanagement and oppression, corporate fraud and provides for speedy trial in public interest. This act makes several provisions regarding money laundering, cheating, forgery, wrongful gain and loss, bank fraud, counterfeiting, credit and insurance etc. Sections 403 to 409 provide for criminal breach of trust and prevent dishonest misappropriation of money. Sections of the IT Act are playing a huge role in keeping a check on cyber-crimes and white collar crimes which are committed using computers as Sections 43 and 44 explain in detail about various crimes and their punishments like illegal extraction of data, hacking, piracy, fraudulent viruses and malicious websites, illegal damage to computer systems, unauthorized and illegal access etc. Black money is used a lot in India and it tops the list. This act defines the crimes but it is the job of the courts to punish the criminals, so the courts should implement it properly without coming under any political pressure. This act

criminalizes all the activities that are related to money laundering and black money. The aim of this act is to eliminate black money in India and convert it into real money. Money laundering increases socio-economic crimes at a very fast pace. Section 38 and 141 are playing a huge role in preventing white collar crimes and this act serves the purpose of decriminalizing various white collar crimes like cheque bouncing, dishonesty, etc. as it makes doing business easier which is a big measure to prevent white collar crimes. It supports the interests of investors and various stakeholders. Apart from this insider trading also plays a big role in increasing white collar crimes. The very famous case of Hindustan Lever is the first case of white collar crimes in which SEBI has punished the defaulters. This act controls white collar crimes related to the trade aspect by providing control over unfair means of import and export. This act prescribes what an auditor has to mandatorily disclose for better transparency and fair means. This law provides for quick and speedy trial which is very necessary in the modern era as the trend of cases involving white collar crimes has increased and the courts have become overburdened with the volume of complaints and cases. This Act protects crimes related to securities transactions. In this act Section 6 of deals with orders that are inconsistent with other acts. Under this act, supervision is done in Delhi Special Police Establishments because nowadays police is not working in white collar crimes cases due to low conviction rate. This act regulates the trade policies of India and deals with import and export laws. It prohibits illegal practices in business sectors. Also, the industrial sector of India is dealing with high rates of white collar issues. This act provides transparent ways to prevent this. Also, it still needs amendments. This act empowers stock exchanges to introduce audit reports in listed entities. Also, it has various provisions that provide a way to control various fraudulent criminal activities. This act also provides for strict provisions related to consumer fraud and malicious fraud committed by shopkeepers and sellers. It brings a strong and healthy market governance system in India and which prevents bribery and deals with various jurisdictions and adjudications related to white-collar crimes like NCLAT. Apart from this, MCA keeps bringing new amendments to keep an eye on reducing white-collar crimes.

Conclusion

White collar crimes are crimes that harm the economy of the entire country. It endangers the country's economy through bank fraud, economic theft, tax evasion, etc. It not only affects the financial condition of a country or an individual, but also has a negative impact on society. Such crimes as bribery, corruption, money laundering and various other crimes have negatively affected the society. White collar crimes have two surprising characteristics, first, they appear to be non-violent crimes, but a great deal of violence is done behind these crimes because when it comes to the result, it is of violent nature, although the criminals have a tendency to gain control or have a sense of authority, and second, they are committed by people with high professions. However, these crimes are also committed by low-paid subordinates, although the mastermind behind such a crime may be a rich person enjoying high social status in his profession. White collar crimes are mostly committed due to peer pressure or due to dependence on corporate culture. As our civilization is approaching modernity and the world is developing new technologies, white collar crime is progressing and the rate of this crime is increasing rapidly. Especially, there has been a huge increase in white collar crimes in the 21st century. These crimes are committed everywhere, in the corporate world, real estate, educational institutions and even in the medical field. Cases of online fraud are also increasing rapidly. Due to these crimes in general and corruption in particular, India, a developing country, is struggling to take its economy towards development. Indian law lacks a clear concept of white collar crime. The government should not be lax in its response to these socio-economic crimes. With regard to white collar crime, the punishment should be strict as these crimes can be prevented to a great extent by harsh punishment. If the crime is very heinous then the punishment can be extended to life imprisonment or death penalty is necessary. Since these crimes do not affect only one person but the entire family and society, like the recent cases of NEET paper leak, UGC NET, have affected not only the candidates but their entire family and society as well as future generations. People are not aware of most of these crimes, so public awareness of this through any means of communication is also necessary. The government should implement strict rules regarding economic theft in the country.

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